

Designing in the Multi-Crises Environment Using the Adaptivity Framework

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Abstract

In light of the ongoing environmental, climate, economic, and social crises, citymaking agents of all disciplines are rethinking the (design of the) built environment with an emphasis on sustainability and inclusivity. While uncertainty and technocratic processes are prevalent, these also present opportunities to explore future scenarios and recognise the proactive role of change in transformative processes. The concept of 'adaptivity', across various design phases and scales, offers a potential approach for envisioning future urban strategies. This article takes an integral approach to examine the different facets of adaptivity and its application in research and design. By addressing the multi-dimensional nature of space and time, this design approach can support the development of diverse methodologies to tackle urgent circular, economic, climate, and social transitions. Moreover, by revisiting existing theories through a review of literature and case studies, the article positions them within today's context and proposes new concepts that go beyond traditional frameworks. Ultimately, this article seeks to enhance our understanding of adaptivity in the built environment, through research and student design projects developed in the Netherlands where its principles are used to respond to changing conditions, showing a thorough collaboration across research, education, and practice.

Keywords

Architecture, urban design, uncertainty, methodology, sustainability, circularity

Introduction

The disciplines shaping the built environment, such as planning, urban design and architecture, have often employed problem-solving, linear approaches. These focus on the needs identified as priorities, triggered by different crises, and associated with paradigms, strategies, and tools active at a specific time. For example, in the post war period, transforming the built environment was motivated by the need to house large numbers of people; today, it has

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to do with the multiple pressures coming from environmental and social stress linked to natural sources deprivation and social justice and inequalities.

Yet the core concepts of the Modernist Movement have continually been simplified and operationalized to deliver standardized, mass-produced solutions, even today. For decades, beyond formal outcomes, this approach has dominated the way cities are constructed. Over time, the focus has transitioned from master-planning the city to strategizing the objects, turning buildings and loose pieces (of infrastructure, for example) into the dominating interests. The consequences are clear: large areas of our inner cities' extensions combine open and built space in random configurations, compact areas coexisting with areas of rigid modernist patterns, which often lack social dimension and human-scale. This all sits in vague in-between areas that continue to extend. For example, in the Netherlands, at the beginning of the 21st century, large parts of its cities revealed a blend of physical and social vacancy, decay, and vulnerability, leaving infill and renovation as the only viable development options.

This is the existing built environment that we are to (re)design if we want to meet the UN Sustainable Development Strategy targets: limiting urban sprawl and land-sealing, regenerating the natural environment, and reducing CO₂ emissions. In addressing one of the major challenges facing many European countries - namely, the housing shortage - we must fundamentally (re)think how we design. Concentrated densification is essential if we are to reduce national housing deficits while simultaneously enabling the climate, energy, and circular transitions needed to tackle today's intertwined environmental and social crises.

In the case of the Netherlands, this concretely means responding to the (ambitious) deal to build one million new houses by 2035. This deal was signed in 2022 by the Dutch Government and its 12 provinces, and includes the requirement that two-thirds of these homes are affordable¹. It also means facing the worsening of climatic conditions related to temperature increase and sea level rise as foreseen by national research agencies² while addressing undefined spatial requirements for future generations as articulated in several scenarios³. Lastly, it also implies the need to relate to the call for circular visions to which many Dutch

¹ Minister Hugo de Jonge, 2022 [See : <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2022/10/13/minister-hugo-de-jonge-maakt-provinciale-woningbouwafspraken-voor-900.000-nieuwe-woningen>]

² It is estimated that by 2050 the temperature in the Netherlands would reach a maximum of +2.3°C more than the 1981-2010 average [See: <https://www.iea.org/articles/netherlands-climate-resilience-policy-indicator>]. Meanwhile, the sea level is expected to rise around 1 meter more than 2021, by 2100 [See: <https://english.deltaprogramma.nl/delta-programme/question-and-answer/what-is-the-situation-regarding-the-rising-sea-level#:~:text=The%20KNMI%20Climate%20Scenarios%20show,of%201%20metre%20by%202100>].

³ Particularly the "Four scenarios for the development of the Netherlands in 2050" produced by PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, [See: [pbl-2024-spatial-scenarios-as-a-tool-for-future-proof-spatial-planning-in-the-netherlands-5593.pdf](#)], and the Climate Scenarios produced by the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) [See: [KNMI - KNMI'23-klimaatscenario's](#)]

municipalities are adhering⁴. Setting this in motion, while we are still quantifying the requirements for those transitions and defining new standards for the construction sector⁵, demands considerable creativity. New solutions must both embrace and update budgetary limitations as well as current governance structures, while also avoiding the oversimplification of impending, dire consequences.

In this context, the sense of urgency felt in the post-war housing production resonates, and the risk of approaching change and new urgencies in a linear-mass production way, is real. But as current densification strategies mobilize within the existing fabric, the inclusion of people is essential. So is the connection between long-term scenarios and site-specific solutions. This calls for a new methodological operational framework. Reasoning with the idea that cities are in a continuous state of change, alongside their inhabitants and the global environment, we developed the *Adaptivity Framework* which we introduce and test in this article.

State of the Art

Linked to their prominent presence in many European cities, numerous renewal and densification projects have in recent years focused on areas of modernist origins. The work of Lacaton and Vassal in France or de Vylder Vinck Taillieu in Belgium offer remarkable examples of how understanding the very genetics of the built stock can endorse interventions that are minimal in their use of resources and maximal in their impact at the environmental and social levels⁶.

It is our view that a reinterpretation of the material and spatial qualities and principles of these areas could feed an innovative approach to transform the built environment, where adaptivity feeds more sustainable and inclusive solutions, so we can move beyond technical or formal aspects. Interestingly, this character was already embedded in the modernist approach, as for example, in the five points of Le Corbusier (*pilotis*, free design of ground plan, façade, horizontal windows, and roof gardens) which give the opportunity to already reflect on customization (plan and facade libre), spatial flexibility, and uses adaptability⁷. This leads to a quest for flexibility and thus to a way of rethinking the relationship between architecture, nature, and open spaces. Later, this was continued through the Metabolism Movement's contributions

⁴ It is an example the urban vision "Amsterdam Circular 2020-2025. Strategy", a strategic tool the Municipality of Amsterdam developed in 2020 and adopted to reduce the use of *new raw materials* in the city by 50 % by 2030, and to make the city 100% circular by 2050 (City of Amsterdam, 2020).

⁵ Both with big ambitions and concrete applications, as testify by the "Implementation Agenda for a Circular Amsterdam" and the Tender Hammerkwartier, stating very exact requirements of % for circular materials in new buildings on the plot requirements.

⁶ See: [Lacaton & Vassal](#) and Hoe start ik mijn onderzoek? | VAI: <https://www.vai.be/advies/onderzoek>

⁷ On the use of different terminology, see Schmidt III & Austin (2016).

to modular architecture and design flexibility (from projects like *City in the Sky*, to the *Nakagin Capsule Tower*); and the speculations of European and American architects such as Yona Friedman. Friedman presented on the occasion of the 10th C.I.A.M. of 1956, with his *Manifeste de l'architecture mobile*, the idea of a flexible architecture that is prone to change by statute. His 'spatial city' proposed a new model of the city, superimposing on the existing so as to preserve the use of land. Within this concept, also the idea of housing is flexible, both in its use (which the architect does not know but which the inhabitant defines for himself), and in its spatial articulation, which follows a system of overlaid grids (Friedman, 1960). Later, John Frazer, during the politically, socially, and economically unstable period of cultural redefinition between the 1960s and 1980s, expressed the need to reflect on new urban systems. Within this framework, interest in recent cybernetics theories and their technological repercussions and a worldview projected towards an often utopian future. From projects such as the *Sky House*, to the *Plug in City* and again to the visionary *The Generator Project*, the desire to go beyond the static treatment of the building, imagining and sometimes constructing those infrastructures (physical and virtual) infrastructures that today form the basis of complex and adaptive systems.

As we see, the very idea of buildings able to change over time has fascinated architects over the last century, creating a shared and vast imaginary connected to advancements in technology (Oosterhuis, 2003). As a result, the terminology used to refer to this kind of architecture has also changed over time, creating an overlapping of meanings both in the literature and in the practice (Kolarevic, 2015). To frame this research, we consider 'adaptive architecture' as a broad concept that refers to the architecture of change and spatial transformation, in response to one or multiple stressors and through different design approaches. We propose that an architecture able to adapt to external or internal circumstances can, in fact, constitute a possible solution to tackle urban challenges, thus resulting in urban development and innovation. This line of thought is not new, but we argue that it can be further stressed and tested in the present context.

In this sense, the theoretical articulations of Habraken are instrumental. With his book *De dragers en de mensen: het einde van de massawoningbouw* (1961), he establishes the basis for a long tradition that reaches us and is based on the ideas of decoupling 'support' and 'infill' in both technical and social ways, with different interfaces between (construction) systems and users being involved in design decision-making. Later, in his work *The Structure of the Ordinary. Form and Control in the Built Environment* (1998), Habraken goes on to define the interwoven orders of Form, Place, and Understanding – which correspond to physical, biological, and social domains – to underpin the creation of territorial relations embracing both the spatial and the social. More specifically, he suggests that the physical construction and structure of the built environment; the boundaries, territorial control, and physical limits; and the social and cultural

aspects of the built environment, including "unspoken conventions"; define shared patterns, and systems of meaning influencing the interactions and shaping of the environment. Habraken continues to feed research at architectonic, urban, and territorial scales, intertwining in work conducted in countries such as Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands and Switzerland. Among them, we could mention that of Kris Scheerlinck on streetscapes territories, Paola Viganò on urban design, and Misselwitz and Schröder on circular urban transformations together with more scholars gathered in the TU Delft Circular Built Environment Hub⁸.

In particular for the architectonic scale, we can reflect on the lesson of Habraken through the work of Frank Duffy (1992) and later Steward Brant (1995), who developed an operational layer model that can be associated with building circularity and sustainability in many of the previously mentioned frameworks. His model emphasises splitting buildings' layers based on their lifespan to achieve higher levels of flexibility when replacing them independently. Some of the experimentations in practice followed through in the Open Building platform, leading to specific skins, vocabularies, and tools, with terms such as fillability, changeability, polyvalency, modularity/demountability⁹, with most of them, associated with the circular R-Strategies (Kirchherr et al., 2017).

As this way of thinking is becoming established in theoretical frameworks and continues to be explored, a lot has been done also in terms of (construction) regulations, as for example the introduction of requirements to include aspects of adaptivity and circularity in public tenders, and the increasing use of material passports and tools such as TOTEM in Belgium that assist the "assessment of the environmental impact of construction elements". This goes hand in hand with new frameworks coming from practice and knowledge institutions such as the TU Delft Flex Adaptive Capacity Assessment Form, and the Calculation Method Adaptive Capacity of Buildings of the Dutch Green Building Counting (DGBC), which, in addition to models coming from policy-making, such as the Deltares/TU Delft's Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways, are approaching the mainstream. In the end, this shows how the search for new balances between flexibility and modular or mass production in the building sector, and how adaptivity, circularity, and sustainability intertwine in these current attempts (Askar et al., 2021). As we conduct this research, several studies have been published on the topic – recently e.g. "The Flexible City.

⁸ For further references check the following links: <https://www.habraken.com/html/introduction.htm> ; <https://streetscapeterritories.org/>; <https://www.studiopaolavigano.eu/publications/>; <https://circularityforeducators.tudelft.nl/article/translating-circularity/>; Circular Built Environment; Home - [Circularity for Educators](#).

⁹ Brand's volume, *How Buildings Learn. What Happens After They're Built*, actually takes up the studies of Frank Duffy published two years earlier in *The Changing Workplace* (Duffy, 1992) and in turn linked to the research of ecologists O'Neil and Salthe on the transfer of mass, energy and information in nature across different time scales. For examples of architectonic projects based on these principles, see: <https://www.openbuilding.co/> and ANA [architecten](#), including their publication on flexible and multifunctional building: https://learningfrommultifunk.files.wordpress.com/2014/08/ana_bookserie_lfm_mail.pdf

Solutions for a Circular and Climate Adaptive Europe” (Bergevoet and van Tuijl, 2024) – thus showing that there is some momentum around such experiments. The question then becomes: is there a way to push this process of exploring non-linear approaches further?¹⁰

Research Gap, Hypothesis, and Research Question

There is a gap that could be decisive in this sense. This lies between Brand’s aforementioned layers model with a focus on the building scale and the technical level, and ideas that embrace the continuity of the built environment (a)s the product of an ongoing, never ending, design process (Habraken, 1961), and further, as the product of ongoing social productions (Bourdieu, 1977). As Habraken’s theoretical elaborations point out (1998), it is the conflicting logics that operate formally and informally, often simultaneously, and at different scales in the built environment that provide new dynamics, including agency and territorialities. We argue further that it is crucial to enlarge the environmental layers and emphasise their intermediate and dynamic conditions (Chiappini, 2021). This strongly contrasts with the idea of ‘eternal’ support (immutable or with a very long mutation pattern) as context is labelled by Brand and moves into more fluctuating interactions between larger layers and agents. At the present time, it becomes increasingly evident that, in a situation of continuous change and the presence of imminent challenges, the premise of an immutable environment is no longer valid.

Reconfiguring the layers of Brand means opening up to new kinds of interactions between scales, and collaborations between disciplines. This way, the multiple disciplines, traditionally linked to roles and professions – namely, architecture and urbanism – are not separated but overlapping. Further, it demands the open exploration and co-creation of multiple processes and projects dynamics where the relations’ environment, city, and buildings are central. As a consequence, more layers that are dynamic and interconnected expand the possibilities to reposition and renew the terms and strategies of adaptivity as a research and design tool in terms of multi-scalarity and multi-disciplinarity.

The hypothesis here is that we can articulate many of the conflicting aspects of current times around adaptivity, and therefore create frameworks to approach the built environment more integrally, openly, and dynamically, with a stronger social component.

¹⁰ For references on these initiatives, see: <https://www.totem-building.be>
<https://research.tudelft.nl/en/publications/flex-30-an-instrument-to-formulate-the-demand-for-and-assessing-t>,
 Methode Adaptief Vermogen Gebouwen - Dutch Green Building Council,
<https://www.deltares.nl/en/expertise/areas-of-expertise/sea-level-rise/dynamic-adaptive-policy-pathways> . The launch of the book coincided also with the opening of a live-cast session programme hosted in Amsterdam by Pakhuis de Zwijger, where the theme of adaptivity in the built environment was discussed over 2023/2024. See: <https://dezwijger.nl/programma/leren-over-de-grens> .

With this, adaptivity can become a crucial (design) approach for co-creation, embedding social inclusiveness. It can also become a *modus operandi* for circular and sustainable spatial transformations at different scales when accommodating new environmental challenges, users' needs, and responding dynamically to changing realities (Andaloro, 2023). This can manifest at every scale of spatial interaction, from the design to the technical; from the architectural to the urban and territorial scales; and can ultimately help overcome siloed-perspectives, integrating experts, users and other agents. Moreover, by developing multi-scalar approaches and integral perspectives, this approach aligns well with the expansion of circular R-Strategies (Kirchherr et al., 2017). By foreseeing this strict connection, we envision the natural predisposition of architecture towards the idea of change, in response to (inner or outer) everchanging conditions or to a shift in the cultural and social landscape.

How can we understand what adaptivity entails at this time? What are the new components leading to new strategies? How can we revise current and past projects and methods to gain insights into new ways to research and design the built environment? Why do we need to build dynamic frameworks that simultaneously contain multiple aspects and open up to new solutions, pathways, and narratives?

These are the research questions that have guided our work over the past two years, and of which we present a snapshot in their theoretical and practical articulations, including applications and case studies in practice, research, and education in this article. In Figure 1, we translate the hypothesis in graphic representations. In the next section, we explain how we tested its application.

Figure 1. Reconfiguration of Brand's layers model. Source: Own production.

Methodology

The reconfiguration of Brand's layers model could contribute to defining a new process for the research and design of the built environment that departs from adaptivity and the possibilities of multi-scalarity and multi-disciplinarity. As a foundation, multiple existing research and design tools that express the core character of adaptivity are catalogued systematically and combined, including built and unbuilt projects of the last century. The

methodology is divided in four phases: (1) building upon this ‘*catalogue*’ from which to (2) extract terms, concepts, principles, and methods, later processed in a ‘*glossary*’. Lastly, (3) we evaluated the different ‘*scales*’ they operate at, addressing the links to those terms and their direct and indirect contribution to adaptivity, resulting in a (4) prototype for research and design, namely the ‘*adaptivity framework*’. In the next sections, we explain in detail how each of these tools can be used in sequence, combinations, or alternated orders. Each of these aspects are not fully independent but multiple interdependencies can be identified between them.

Catalogue

Cataloguing exemplary designed or built projects from the last century lays the groundwork for understanding the diverse facets of adaptivity. In a digital online platform, the catalogue serves to create clusters to connect theory, practice, and case studies. In its current state, the catalogue combines around 60 projects, chosen based on their relevance in the adaptivity context, and catalogued according to three main groups of information (Figure 2):¹¹

- Contextual information, as related to the author(s), the time of design or construction, status of the project, place of the project;
- Specific adaptivity type, which highlights the presence of different nuances of adaptivity, related to a (time-specific) terminology;
- Scale of reference, related to building, city, and network levels.

Figure 2. Catalogue of Adaptive Architecture, as from the online website available at: <https://adaptive-architecture.notion.site>. Source: Own production

¹¹ At the current stature, the catalogue includes 42 built projects, 3 in construction phase, 2 demolished, and 20 between competition project, project not realised and prototypes. The database has been built on Notion and is also accessible online at: <https://adaptive-architecture.notion.site>. The Database is meant for being continuously updated through the support of students, researchers and all those who are interested in the approach, via an online form.

Glossary

By connecting the design examples in the catalogue to the literature, we can distil the common terminologies related to the idea of adaptivity and generate a glossary of ‘adaptive architecture’ (AA). The terms listed below are sometimes related to the performance of spatial structures, and in that sense also linked to the research and design process as discussed up until now. The projects included belong to a broad geographical boundary, mainly renowned cases of both new projects and redesign or renewal. This is aimed at considering different nuances of the architecture of spatial change.

Adaptable: Adaptable architecture can be modified and transformed in relation to endogenous needs, related to the inhabitants and users (Lelieveld et al., 2007). The space is designed in a way to allow for changes over time, often thanks to the use of modular structures or elements. Adaptable architecture is multi-functional and multi-temporal. Examples are projects like Diagoonwoningen (Herman Hertzberger, 1970, Delft), Benthemplein Water square (De Urbanisten, 2012, Rotterdam), and Superblocks Examples (Ajuntamiento Barcelona, 2016, Barcelona).

Flexible: Flexible architecture can be modified and transformed in relation to exogenous needs, related to the environment or uses (Groak, 1992; Schneider and Till, 2007). The space is designed both in technicalities and performability, in a way to allow for spatial changes during the life of the project, in order to accommodate users’ spatial needs or to better cope with external stressors (Schmidt III, 2106). By using movable elements (such as walls or furniture), the design is often customised and site-specific, as in the case of Sky House (Kionori Kikutake, 1960, Tokyo), Storefront for Art and Architecture (Steven Holl, 1993, New York), and The Shed (Diller & Scofidio + Renfro, 2008-2019, New York).

Interactive: Interactive architecture (iA) is constituted more philosophically, as its assumed capability of triggering a ‘two-way dialogue’ between human beings and built elements (Oosterhuis et al., 2007). Among transformable architectures, interactive architecture first benefited from the digital and information technology turn in architecture. Defined at the beginning of 2000 as an evolution of intelligent architecture in relation to responsive environments (Fox & Kemp, 2009), iA has been mostly explored through Media Architecture, as a means to create liminal spaces between the physical and the digital world, as in the case of Wind Tower (Toyo Ito, 1986, Yokohama, 1999).

Modular: The concept of modular architecture has been strictly tied to the constructive system which, with the increase of mass production, has been increasingly standardized. As a result, modular architecture opened up the design and build of aggregated units, resulting in solutions which can be reshaped over time. The module, then, can eventually coincide with the

structural system, as in the case of Nakagin Capsule Tower (Kisho Kurokawa, 1970, Tokyo), Spatial City (Yona Friedman, 1958), and The Urban Village Project (EFFEKT Architects, 2018). These can be assembled within a structural frame, or they can themselves embed the structural system.

Adaptive: Adaptive architecture manifests a spatial physical capacity to respond to external stressors, perceived and understood via devices or infrastructures (Schnädelbach, 2010; Ulber, 2019). This definition is often associated with responsiveness from which it is distinguished by the introduction of the variable of time in the transformation processes (Elmokadem, et al, 2018). Adaptive architecture changes independently, dynamically, and in real time, to fluctuations in certain external conditions, establishing a two-way relationship between the environment, people, and the actual architectural fabric (Kolarevic and Parlac, 2015). Adaptive architecture can be illustrated with projects such as Blur building (Diller & Scofidio, 2002, Yverdonne-les-Bains, Al Bahar Towers (Aedas, 2012, Abu Dhabi), and Jade Eco Park (Philippe Rahm, 2019, Taichung).

Predictive: The capability of architecture to be predictive is increasingly common in adaptive design due to the use of data and technology to predict or anticipate different aspects of the built environment. Predictive architecture can be referred to as performance simulation models, so as to predict external changes and adapt the built elements' behaviour towards them (Kim and Johanes, 2023). It can also be used during the design phase as a way to envision specific local conditions and their changes overtime, so to adapt the project to them (Bhatt et al., 2016), as in the case of The Generator Project (Cedric Price, 1976, White Oak Plantation) and (Un) Plug (François Roche, 2001, Paris).

Generative: Generative architecture is an iterative, guided, and explorative design approach that allows a wide range of possible solutions to be shaped from parametric constraints (Sivam, 2011). It is based on the combination of computerized processes and artificial intelligence, and is triggered from advanced algorithms, which indicate the constraints and objectives that the design must meet. In this sense, this approach refers to so-called 'evolutionary' techniques for defining design solutions, either through selection mechanisms or algorithmic processes (or rules) that generate multiple, complex solutions (Bernal et al., 2005; Fischer, et al., 2018), as in the projects Aspiration (François Roche, 1998, Venice), or Media-TIC (Enric Ruiz-Geli & Cloud 9, 2012, Barcelona). The impact of the new generation of generative and multi-model algorithms have yet to materialize in actual built architecture, but will surely have a large impact.

Eco-based (Nature-based): Eco-based architecture refers to the vast use of nature-based solutions¹² as a way to deal with the changing stressors in the different environments through natural elements, primarily within green infrastructure (European Commission, 2015). Through the application of Nature-based Solutions (NbS), it aims to develop environmental, social, and economic benefits. This approach often shifts the point of view of the design, suggesting an adaptive (built) environment to cope with environmental and/or climate stressors, as in the case of Hygroskin Meteorosensitive Pavilion (ICS, 2013, FRAC Orleans) and Hans Tavsén and Korsgade Park (SLA, 2016, Copenhagen).

Scales

The understanding of the concept of adaptivity has evolved over time but also has different meanings in space. We differentiate three scales and their relations between different spatial aspects: the small/building scale, the medium/city scale, and the big/network scale.

Small/Building Scale: At the building scale, AA represents the capability of spatial layouts in relation to changing users' and transitional needs. These capabilities are distributed among different architectonic devices such as walls, facades, systems (HVAC), floors, and windows, which reflect people's behaviour. This also includes the performance of the architecture itself, as for example, how the actual building is performing in terms of sustainability, greening, and heat reductions. Over the decades, AA at this scale has shown how it is possible to contribute to a more resilient environment by exploring variations on typologies and technologies (Schmidt III & Austin, 2016).

Medium/City Scale: At the city scale, AA is the capability of the urban system to cope with external environmental, social, political stress by the means of spatial elements. Through the transformation of public spaces or infrastructure, AA redefines the space and seeks to impact people's lives (Manigrasso, 2019). At this scale, AA also impacts on shaping and revising neighbourhood typologies, by promoting new ways to live that can respond to the societal challenges of inclusivity and sustainability.

Big/Network Scale: AA contributes to the creation of adaptive networks, in which adaptivity can be further explored through new digital, artificial, and intelligent tools which enable the creation of a structured branching of information and data, contributing to the physical transformation of the (extra)urban, public and private environment (Spyropoulous, 2013).

Combining the catalogue, the glossary and the spatial distribution, a graphical representation has been constructed to explore the intertwining of adaptivity (Figure 3). In a

¹² The prominent reference terminology is Nature-Based Solution (NbS or NbD, Nature-Based Design), but it also includes research field related (not exclusively) to biomimetic, biomorphic, or bio-robotic architecture.

‘spiral of time’, 60 projects are positioned in chronological order, and connected to their design-approach and their related scale. This illustrates the evolution of adaptive architecture, different theories, materials and technologies, and the broadening of projects towards inter-scalar and interdisciplinary networks. The graphic representation serves an additional purpose too, i.e. to stimulate an open conversation between different actors in projects and perspectives on adaptivity.

Figure 3. Adaptive Architecture: Concepts & Methods. Graphical Piece. Source: Own production

Framework

Based on the analysis, we have developed an ‘adaptivity framework’ (AF). This is intended as a means of approaching current societal and environmental challenges through a structured design and research methodology that remains dynamic, open, and socially engaged. The main goal of the AF is thus to relate both to (applied) research and design processes in practice, as well as educational and research settings, defining possible means of understanding the

complexity of adaptive projects. The AF is intended as a collaborative tool, which can support inductive processes, such as design development processes (as in education, i.e.), or deductive approaches, as in research. It engages with real life case studies, thus allowing for long-term, scenario-based, site-specific, and strategic solutions to take place (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Adaptive Architecture Design Framework, graphical elaboration. Source: Own production

As illustrated, the AF comprises four separate ‘branches’, all individually related to the (architectural) project, and representing four main aspects: (1) ‘dimension’, (2) ‘design approach’, (3) ‘domains’, and (4) ‘design resources’. These branches can be explored independently or in relation to each other, and in different sequences.

1. Dimensions (further divided in ‘time’, ‘space’, and ‘scale’): allow us to position the project according to its objective temporal and spatial coordinates; the other three branches support the experimentation in a design process that aims to tackle the built environment simultaneously in multiple societal challenges.

2. Design Approach: relates to the possibility of adaptive architecture to be expressed through different nuances of approaches, as lined out in the glossary.

3. Domains: mainly refer to the different societal challenges. For example social, involving poverty issues, and the claim for equity; economy, involving energy policies and management, resources scarcity, city supplies management, and the just transition; ecology/environment, claiming for sustainability and resilience, involving de-carbonization, improvement of renewable sources and decrease of soil usage, the definition of circular economy systems, scarcity of

materials; climate, involving temperature increase, heat waves, sea level rise, wind peaks, drought, and flooding. This list can be subdivided and specified to the search at stake.

4. Design Resources: this branch highlights the specific perspective through which the project could be developed, claiming for the definition of a methodology. The options outlined in the AF illustrate different ways to relate design and research. As for example, employing ‘Research-through-Design’ (RtD) allows for developing knowledge through the design process itself (Frayling, 1993). Whereas, ‘Design-by-Research’ as a method implies pre-existing research knowledge to inform design solutions (Buchanan, 1992). Moreover, designing with a ‘problem-solving’ approach requires a generative process of developing and selecting variants of possibilities which contribute to the test and solve the main issue (Ellamil, 2012). A "scenario-based" method, instead, is essential for understanding the challenges in defining a specific development trajectory within the climatic, geographical, social, or economic domain involved. It emphasizes the need for planning in the face of uncertainty, acknowledging that these factors cannot be fully predicted or controlled (Eilouti, 2018).¹³

The application of this AF offers structured pathways to explore opportunities to transform the built environment, rethinking Brand’s layers and developing a new vision to address future uncertainties. With this scope in mind, we have been testing different methodologies to achieve this, as we will explain in the next section.

Applications and Case Studies

The AF is an iterative tool to support applied research and design processes in education and research. It allows the exploration of different aspects of a design or research challenge in a methodological way, while simultaneously opening up to further explorations and bifurcations within and beyond those aspects. It also offers the possibility to (re)position elements in relationship to each other, and to generate new narratives. This can become a tool for negotiation and co-production. Further, it allows the deconstruction of case studies, reference projects and narratives (by different actors, for example) to understand the intrinsic conformations linked to larger challenges, reinforcing in this way, their visualization and co-production possibilities.

Next, we explored how the framework can be used for applied research and educational design, and different scales, from the building, (existing) neighbourhood, and city. This work has not been produced independently, but in collaboration with practice. A list of involved partnerships and participants can be found in the acknowledgements section.

¹³To deepen this topic, you can focus on the work of Richard Buchanan (1992) and Ellamil et al. (2012).

Adaptive Existing Neighbourhoods: Forgotten Neighbourhoods (Research Project)

This is a research project focusing on a postwar neighbourhood built in the 70s and 80s. We first analysed the spatial components of the expected transition challenges for energy, biodiversity, climate change, circularity, mobility and social inclusiveness as drafted in national-regional and local legislation and policy ambitions. We translated those expectations into spatial requirements at building and neighbourhood level, in order to quantify and visualize them in concrete terms. In order to understand the spatial-programmatic and social challenges of the neighbourhoods, we researched and documented this in in-depth catalogues of 16 cases around the country, located in larger and smaller cities as diverse as Amsterdam, Haarlem, Rotterdam, Eindhoven, and Heerlen. They include historical developments (from pre-urban landscapes to recent developments), morphological composition thought scales, from the different urban layers, to the building and housing typologies. They also highlight social and symbolic aspects translated into demographics and projects already implemented or planned for the areas. With this, we can see the possibilities for (re)development and densification influenced by those transitions. We acquire different strategies based on the continuation and break up of their composition's internal principles, through, for example, embracing informal growth logics, the reinforcement of their dominating formal structures, the emphasis placed on social upgrading by quantifying fluxes and fixities. Figure 5 illustrates how this project can be included in the AF, determined by the specific qualities and processes at stake in the neighbourhoods, while Figure 6 provides an overview of the 16 cases.

Previous publications provide more details (Chiappini & Suurenbroek, 2024 and 2025), but as a conclusion of the use of the framework, it can be highlighted that in this case, making the relationship between the Dimension and the Design Resources explicit (first and fourth "branch") opened doors to speculate on the Design Approach and to address urgent Domains pressing these areas (second and third "branch").

Figure 5. Forgotten Neighbourhoods: AF. Source: Own production

Figure 6. Forgotten Neighbourhoods (Research Project): Cases at scale of analysis (per case). Source: Own production

Adaptive Building: Dialogue Model (Research Project)

The dialogue model is a physical model at 1:100 scale that includes a variety of building complexes and their immediate surroundings at both street and open space levels. It is a tool to make concrete choices, via the visualisation and spatialization in square and cubic meters surfaces and objects, the requirements of different transitions affecting space, focussing on

energy, biodiversity, water, climate adaptation, and social inclusivity. With this concrete representation, it is possible to study their interaction and friction points, and to start envisioning the new resources and innovation needed. Technically, this is achieved by the interaction between a framework system representing the buildings, floors, and facades structures, and a modular system where individual and assembled objects of different textures and thickness stand for the different technical elements. This way, one can have a concrete experience of the different layers that could interconnect in a green facade, or the scarcity issue on the roof when applying energy, water, and nature in negotiation. Starting from the Adaptivity Framework to highlight different searches and negotiations, we hope that in the future, this system develops into an operational tool (Figures 7-8). Here, the emphasis on the specific Dimensions of the building-city scales (first “branch”), opens the possibility to visualize aspects of the Design Resources (fourth “branch”) and from there, use scenario-based and problem-solving methods in combination with concrete Design Approaches (second “branch”) to embrace the Domains that change from case to case (third “branch”). Other publications present in more detail how this is implemented as a dialogue tool between different specialists (Chiappini & Suurenbroek, 2024).

Figure 7. Dialogue Model: AF. Source: Own production

Figure 8. Dialogue Model: Picture in the HvA Urban Design Lab. Source: Own production.

Adaptive City: Minor Future-Proof Cities, Case Almere Pampus (Educational Assignment)

This is a student project developed in partnership with the Municipality of Almere where students from AUAS are asked to feed the speculations and discussions on the extension plan for the Pampus area, where more than 35.000 houses and 16.000 working places are to be located. The proposal begins by acknowledging the inevitability of risk in the area, due to its vulnerability to flooding and climate hazards. Instead of considering this a problem, it is accentuated and used as a departure point for design. The natural topography is accentuated to include areas where water is welcome permanently, areas that are to remain dry, and areas that can potentially cope with the intermittent presence of water. This leads to a new definition of building typologies and public spaces (roads, facilities, and open spaces) that creatively embrace such changing circumstances. The range of design outcomes is enlarged and the experience of navigating such a natural-urban area, is a provocation of what could become normal in the future. Figures 9 and 10 show how focusing on specific areas and narratives influenced the outcomes. As for the AF, we see that a delimitation of the accentuated components on the different “branches” can also provide the “red threat” of the narrative of this specific proposal.

Figure 9. Minor Future-Proof Cities, Case Almere Pampus: AF. Source: Own production

Figure 10. Minor Future-Proof Cities, Case Almere Pampus. Students Visualizations. Source: Own production

Adaptive Neighbourhood: Integral Project Hamerkwartier (Educational Assignment)

This is a student project developed for an area in North Amsterdam where in a collection of new buildings, a considerable amount of housing units is to be developed. The consortium included local craftsmanship companies, NGOs, different level authorities, and practitioners to rethink the implementation of an existing tender in a focus area. The outcomes demonstrate how including concepts of adaptivity both at the building and neighbourhood scale can lead to an expansion of the possibilities of use and configurations of public space. The framework here is used to emphasise and explore the different aspects that the proposal addresses, especially

through the use of different scenarios at city level. Figures 11 and 12 highlight the focus points in relation to the AF and an overview of their spatial possibilities.

Figure 11. Integral Project Hamerkwartier: AF. Source: Own production

Figure 12. Integral Project Hamerkwartier: Students Visualizations. Source: Own production

Adaptive Building: Graduation Studio Amstel Station (Educational Assignment)

These graduation projects are part of the ‘Atelier 100% Circular”, with a focus on adaptive building. A project developed in the Amstel station area of Amsterdam, this illustrates how including adaptivity directly from the origin of the design process can lead to dynamic spatial configurations. We see modularity and multifunctionality at the building scale brought to a level that not only solves a programmatic challenge but also becomes the very aesthetic expression

of the proposal. Figures 13 and 14 show the focus points of the project in relation to the AF, and how it enables and enlarges the search possibilities in spatial terms. In this case, a focused work on the Design Approaches produced a building that is adaptable, flexible, and modular at its maximum expression.

Figure 13. Graduation Studio Amstel Station: AF. Source: Own production

Figure 14. Graduation Studio Amstel Station: Students Visualizations. Source: Own production

Discussion

The case studies and tools presented here illustrate the operationalisation of adaptive design and research approaches across scales – from buildings to neighbourhoods and cities – each testing specific responses to intertwined societal challenges. Together, they underline the

versatility of rethinking adaptivity in a new framework, exploring new capacities to integrate different methods and scales into specific pathways for solutions.

The Adaptive Framework, and by extension this paper, acknowledges a specific research trajectory on adaptivity in architecture, and provides an opportunity to test the limitations, potentials, and future directions of such an operational tool. What emerges prominently is a variety of discussions, which we introduce briefly, and which find a visual representation in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Reinterpretation of Brand's layers model. Source: Own production

The first of these concerns the role of adaptivity as a character of architecture able to influence the design process. The diverse and complex societal challenges we currently experience suggest the reconfiguration of Brand's and Duffy's Shearing Layers. Building on René Heijne and Jacques Vink's adaptation of the diagram (Heijne & Vink, 2005) – where the thickness of each layer is adjusted to reflect their durability – and our own elaborations presented earlier, we explored how to embed these aspects critically, taking into account the interrelation between the layers.

Conventional construction, from which the ancient idea of architecture being durable is derived (building on the Roman concept of *Venustas*), is strictly connected to the integration and combination of the inner layers. This presents some clear advantages, which can lead to ease of change, but also highlights a structural, functional, and often spatial inflexibility of the space. Conversely, adaptive designs, similar to circularity, benefit from decoupling the layers, enabling repairs, replacements, or adaptations without disrupting other elements. This interplay of connection and autonomy among the layers also facilitates the reconsideration of the

foundational 'site' layer, upon which all others depend. Traditionally considered the most durable structure, tied to place and footprint (Van Reet, 2005), the site layer can itself be reimagined not only at architectonic but at urban and environmental scale. By interpreting the layers through the lens of the Adaptivity Framework, we combine the potential for interconnecting layers while preserving their unique, adaptive qualities, thus supporting innovative and actual design practices. Moreover, the framework tackles also the R-strategies principles, as operative principles for translating adaptive thinking into design action. Specifically, while highlighting the strong potential of new strategies such as 'Re-imagine', 'Re-think', and 'Re-purpose', this research aims to trigger a discussion on the possibility of revisiting existing structures and systems, thus uncovering new meanings and possible Rs (Chiappini and Abujidi, 2023). Through this regenerative logic, adaptive architecture is presented as a process of continuous reinterpretation and renewal, able to rethink the lifespan and agency of the built environment. This analysis underscores a growing interest in both research and practice, questioning the role of architecture in a broad sense, as well as of design as a catalyst for change.

Secondly, this paper also reveals some of the limits of the research, especially concerning its application at (intermediate) scales of the urban tissue, including deeper levels of theoretical and methodological articulations. However, future advancements could focus on expanding the framework's conceptual and practical tools to address specific contextual challenges more effectively (Andaloro, Chiappini & Suurenbroek, 2024; 2025), thus emphasising the exploration of circularity in practice, education, and research.

Lastly, the openness of the Adaptive Framework allows for a reflection on the embedding of new(er) digital and intelligent tools into the different phases of design. By incorporating adaptive technologies and predictive modelling into the design, the framework could serve as a (knowledge) structure to understand and, eventually, to respond to unforeseen stressors, thus enabling dynamic recalibration as conditions evolve. With the support of Machine Learning models and AI technology, the adaptiveness of a design process could, in fact, be predicted through design scenarios (Buckton et al., 2023), in a more complex and multi-scalar regeneration design process.

Ultimately, this paper marks a starting point for formalising insights gained through applied practice, research, and education experimentation in design. By detailing the iterative processes behind these projects, we invite you to further explore how adaptive principles can guide the long-term impact of the current rapid transformations within the material and immaterial space of the built environment.

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References

- Andaloro, B. (2023). *I caratteri dell'architettura resiliente adattiva. Invarianti compositive del progetto: 1990-2020* [Doctoral Dissertation], University of Palermo, Italy.
- Andaloro, B. & Chiappini, M. C. (2024). *From the Open City to the Open Network: How Adaptive Architecture is Shaping the Architectural Transitions*. AMS Conference: Reinventing the City [Contribution]. Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions, Amsterdam.
- Andaloro, B., Chiappini, M. C. & Suurenbroek, F. (2025). *Framework for Adaptive Spatial Transformations in Times of Multiple Crises*. DOKORP 2025 Conference: Raumplanung [Contribution], TU Dortmund.
- Andaloro, B., Chiappini, M. C. & Suurenbroek, F. (2025). *Designing in the Multi-Crises Environment through the Adaptivity Framework*. 19th AESOP Young Academics Conference [Contribution], Faculty of Architecture and Landscape Sciences (FAL), Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz University Hannover.
- Askar, R., Bragança, L. & Gervásio, H. (2021). Adaptability of Buildings: A Critical Review on the Concept Evolution, In: *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, 1-32.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app11104483>
- Bergevoet, T. & van Tuijl, M. (2016). *The Flexible City. Sustainable Solutions for a Europe in Transition*. Nai010 Publishers, Rotterdam.
- Bergevoet, T. & van Tuijl, M. (2023). *The Flexible City. Solutions for a Circular and Climate Adaptive Europe*. Nai010 Publishers, Rotterdam.
- Bernal, M., Haymaker, J.R., Eastman, C. (2005). On the role of computational support for designers in action. *Design Studies*, 41, 163-182.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2015.08.001>
- Bijndendijk, F. (2005). *Solids*, in: Leupen, B., Heijne, R., van Zwol, J. *Time-based Architecture. Architecture able to withstand changes through time. Architecture able to withstand changes through time*. Nai 010 Publisher, Rotterdam, pp. 42-51.
- Bhatt, M., Suchan, J., Schultz, C., Kondyli, V. & Goyal, S. (2016). Artificial Intelligence for Predictive and Evidence Based Architecture Design. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 30(1), 4349-4350.
<https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v30i1.9850>
- Bourdieu, P. (1977). *Cultural Reproduction and Social Reproduction*. In J. Karabel, & A. H. Halsey (Eds.), *Power and Ideology in Education* (pp. 487-511). Oxford University Press, New York.
- Buchanan, r. (1992). Wicked Problems in Design Thinking. *Design Issues*, 8(2), 5-21
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/1511637>
- Buckton, S. J., Fazey, I., Sharpe, B., Om, E. S., Doherty, B., Ball, P., Denby, K., Bryant, M., Lait, R., Bridle, S., Cain, M., Carmen, E., Collins, L., Nixon, N., Yap, C., Connolly, A., Fletcher, B., Frankowska, A., Gardner, G., James, A., Kendrick, I., Kluczkovski, A., Mair, S., Morris, B. & Sinclair, M. (2023). The Regenerative Lens: A conceptual framework for regenerative social-ecological systems, One Earth.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.06.006>
- Brand, S. (1994). *How Buildings Learn: What Happens After They're Built*. Viking Press.
- City of Amsterdam (2020). Amsterdam Circular 2020-2025. Strategy. Report.
https://assets.amsterdam.nl/publish/pages/1043702/amsterdam-circular-2020-2025-public_version.pdf
- Chiappini, M. C. (2021). *Infrastructure under Transformation as Spaces of Collectivities. Glòries, Barcelona, Spain*. [Doctoral Dissertation], KU Leuven, Brussels.

- Chiappini, M.C. & Suurenbroek, F. (2024). *Dialoog Maquette: Workshop*. AMS Conference: Reinventing the City [Contribution]. Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions, Amsterdam.
- Chiappini, M.C. & Suurenbroek, F. (2025). *Forgotten Neighborhoods*. DOKORP 2025 Conference: Raumplanung [Contribution], TU Dortmund.
- Chiappini, M.C. & Suurenbroek, F. (2025). *Vergeten Wijken, Kansrijke Ruimte Inventariserend onderzoek naar de jaren '70-'80 woonwijken met sociale huurwoningen - en de opgaven en kansen van herstructurering: White Paper*. HvA, Amsterdam.
- Duffy, F. (1992). *The Changing Workplace*. Phaidon Press, UK.
- Ellamil, M., Dobson, C., Beeman, N., & Christoff, K. (2012). Evaluative and generative modes of thought during the creative process. *NeuroImage*, vol 59, pp. 1783-1794
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2095263518300426>
- Elmokadem, A., Ekram, M., Waseef, A. & Nashaat, B. (2018). Kinetic Architecture: Concepts, History and Applications. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 7(4), 750–758. <https://www.doi.org/10.21275/ART20181560>
- European Commission (2015). *Towards an EU research and innovation policy agenda for nature-based solutions & re-naturing cities – Final report of the Horizon 2020 expert group on 'Nature-based solutions and re-naturing cities'*, Publications Office of the European Union. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/479582>
- Fischer, T. & Herr, C. (2001). Teaching generative design. In: *The Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Generative Art 2001*. Milan, Italy, pp. 1-14.
- Fox, M. & Kemp, M. (2009). *Interactive Architecture*. Princeton Architectural Press, Princeton.
- Friedman, Y. (1960). *L'Architecture Mobile. 10 principes d'urbanisme spatiale, an addition to the manifesto published in 1958*, Les presses du reel, Paris.
- Habraken, N. J. (1961). *De dragers en de mensen: het einde van de massawoningbouw*. Scheltema & Holkema, Amsterdam.
- Habraken, N. J. (1998). *The Structure of the Ordinary, Form and Control in the Built Environment*. MIT Press, Boston.
- Heijne, R. & Vink, J. (2005) Flex-buildings, designed to respond to change. In: Leupen, B., Heijne, R., van Zwol, J. *Time-based Architecture. Architecture able to withstand changes through time. Architecture able to withstand changes through time*. Nai 010 Publisher, Rotterdam, pp. 58-67.
- Kim, F., & Johanes, M. (2023). Text2Form Diffusion: Framework for learning curated architectural vocabulary. In: *Proceedings of the 41st Conference on Education and Research in Computer Aided Architectural Design in Europe (eCAADe 2023)*, pp. 79-88. <https://doi.org/10.52842/conf.ecaade.2023.1.079>
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D. & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 127, p. 221–232.
- Kolarevic, B. & Parlac, V. (2015). *Building Dynamics: Exploring Architecture of Change*, Routledge: Taylor & Francis, New York. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315763279>
- Krish, S. (2011). A practical generative design method. In: *Computer-Aided Design*, 43 (1), 88–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cad.2010.09.009>
- Lelieveld, C., Voorbij, A. & Poolman, W. (2007). Adaptable architecture. In: Kitsutaka, Y. (Eds.) *Building stock activation, Proceedings of International conference of 21st century COE Program of Tokyo Metropolitan University*, TAIHEI Printing Co, 245–252.
- Maccreeanor (2005) The sustainable city is the adaptable city. In: Leupen, B., Heijne, R., van Zwol, J. *Time-based Architecture. Architecture able to withstand changes through time*.

- Architecture able to withstand changes through time*. Nai 010 Publisher, Rotterdam, pp. 98-109.
- Manigrasso, M. (2019). *La città adattiva: il grado zero dell'urban design*, Città e paesaggio, Quodlibet, Macerata.
- Oosterhuis, K. (2003). *Hyperbodies. IT revolution in architecture*, Birkhäuser, Basel.
- Oosterhuis, K., Xia, X., & Jap Sam, E. (2007). *Interactive Architecture #1*, Episode publisher, Serie iA.
- Reet (van), B. (2005) Cultural durability. In: Leupen, B., Heijne, R., van Zwol, J. *Time-based Architecture. Architecture able to withstand changes through time. Architecture able to withstand changes through time*. Nai 010 Publisher, Rotterdam, pp. 110-115.
- Schmidt III, R. & Austin, S. (2016). *Adaptable Architecture: Theory and Practice*, Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, New York. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315722931>
- Schnädelbach, H. (2010). Adaptive Architecture – A Conceptual Framework. In: *Proceedings of MediaCity: Interaction of Architecture, Media and Social Phenomena*, 523–556. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2875452>
- Schneider, T. & Till, J. (2007). *Flexible Housing*. Architectural Press, Oxford.
- Shea, K., Aish, R., & Gourtovaia, M. (2005). Towards integrated performance-driven generative design tools. In: *Automation in Construction*, 14, 253-264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2004.07.002>
- Spyropoulos, T., & Schumacher, P. (2013). *Adaptive Ecologies: Correlated Systems of Living*, Architectural Association, London.
- Steven G. (1992). *The Idea of Building*, London, E&FN Spon, 1992, pp. 154-7. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203133781>
- Ulber, M. (2019). Adaptive architecture as mediator between humans and earth. *AGATHÓN | International Journal of Architecture, Art and Design* 6, pp. 94–103. <https://doi.org/10.19229/2464-9309/692019>